

**Second Annual Conference on
Applied Management and Decision Sciences
(AMDS 2006)**

Building a Research Agenda for the 21st Century

Friday, January 20, 2006, Dallas, Texas, USA

**Sponsored by the School of Management
Walden University**

Larry Beebe, Ph.D.
Conference Chair

Anna Wasescha, Ph.D.
Conference Coordinator

Raghu B. Korrapati, Ph.D.
Conference Manager

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Agenda

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|------------------------|--|
| 8:00 – 8:45 AM | Conference Opening - Dallas Ballroom A1

Dr. John Vinton
Dean, School of Management,

Presentation by Keynote Speaker

Dr. Cesar Morales
Institutional Rector of the Universidad del Valle de Mexico |
| 8:45 – 9:00 AM | Conference Overview

Dr. Larry Beebe
Conference Chair |
| 9:05 – 10:35 AM | Conference Presentations – Dallas Ballrooms A1 and A2 |
| 10:35 – 10:55 AM | Break |
| 10:55 AM –
12:05 PM | Conference Presentations – Dallas Ballrooms A1 and A2 |
| 12:10 – 1:10 PM | Lunch and Guest Speaker – Houston Ballroom

Dr. Javier Fadul
“Corporate Social Responsibility and International Business” |
| 1:15 – 3:15 PM | Conference Presentations – Dallas Ballrooms A1 and A2 |
| 3:15 – 3:30 PM | Break |
| 3:30 – 4:45 PM | Conference Presentations – Dallas Ballrooms A1 and A2 |
| 4:45 – 5:00 PM | Conference Closing – Dallas Ballroom 1 |

**POST-IMPLEMENTATION ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT
PROGRAMS AT GOVERNMENT ORGANIZATIONS: THE GSA CASE**

Dallas Ballroom A2

Firend Al R. Walden University
and Sherrie Householder

Abstract

This paper examines the causes of failure in post-implementation of knowledge management programs at large government organizations, specifically the case of the Goods and Services Agency (GSA) as knowledge management strategy embodies a long-standing scheme involving not only technology integration but also considerable investment in change management and business process design. The paper further suggests that KM programs in traditional government organizational structures often fail to deliver results in complex, multi-enterprise organizational structures because KM initiatives seek to transform the entire understanding of work processes, which causes workers to avoid utilizing KM systems effectively. Findings in this paper concludes that several elements contributed to the failure of implementation of KM programs at large government organizations, reasons seen as; lack of strategic direction and/or leadership, organizational environment and culture, the silo effect, and technology enabler and disabler, can greatly hinder KM initiatives.